

CHALLENGING CURRENT URBAN LIGHTING POLICIES: CASE FOR A SHIFT OF FOCUS TO ALERTNESS

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INTRODUCTION: CURRENT RESEARCH ON STREET LIGHTING FOR PEDESTRIANS IS HEAVILY FOCUSED ON VISUAL PERFORMANCE. WE ARGUE THAT MORE RESEARCH IS NEEDED ON OTHER PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS ALSO IMPORTANT FOR PEDESTRIANS' ATTENTION AND SAFETY – ALERTNESS, AROUSAL AND ANXIETY.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK PROPOSAL: MAIN PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS – ALERTNESS, AROUSAL AND ANXIETY – ARE DISCUSSED AND CLARIFIED. WE PROPOSE A DIFFERENT FOCUS OF RESEARCH ON THE EFFECTS OF URBAN LIGHTING FOR PEDESTRIANS.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK APPLICATION: THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK IS EXPLAINED ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE BURTT [1] STUDY AND A RECENT PILOT STUDY.

CONCLUSIONS: FINDINGS FROM OUR PILOT STUDY WARRANT FURTHER RESEARCH ON THE CONCEPTS PROPOSED IN OUR THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK. WE MAKE A CASE FOR URBAN LIGHTING POLICIES TO TAKE INTO ACCOUNT THE CONCEPTS OF ALERTNESS, AROUSAL AND ANXIETY.

Keywords: arousal; alertness; anxiety; urban lighting; safety